

Scalability of Qur’anic Meanings through a new method of Attribute-Oriented Object Recognition

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Abstract

Any sincere transmitted message must have an explicit addressee, an intended meaningful message, and a feasible language of communication. Mingling these three distinct facts results in some failure in refining the message. We applied this self-evident rule to Qur’an as the ‘sincere message’ sent by God to all of humanity, carrying whatever intended meaning(s), and expressed in the Arabic language. We found that this rule was distorted and restricted the ‘Qur’anic global universal’ message into ‘a local Arabic cultural one’. The anticipated outcome manifests itself into a series of challenges that greatly intensified in this modern age. After enumerating the challenges, we present a detailed methodology in terms of ‘Scalability of Qur’anic Meanings’, through which we reset the communication process of the message back to its original global state, with clear separation of the “addressee’ culture” from the “language of communication”. In this new methodology, we focus on the explicit duality of Quranic verses, as given in verse (3:7), into ‘evident’ and ‘equivocal’ verses, where emphasis is put on the equivocal verses as the key that switches the message back to its global nature, as it should. The core of our resolution is based on transferring equivocal verses into evident verses, whenever possible, through a method of recognizing the objects of speech of the verses by their explicit attributes in the Qur’anic text. Thus, we name it “The Method of Attribute-Oriented Object Recognition”. Lastly, we show how to apply this method to uncover hidden meanings in the Qur’anic text.

Introduction and Methodology:

By ‘scalability of Qur’anic meanings’ we mean to move from a small domain of interpretability of its equivocal verses, upon acquisition of more relevant ‘natural’ data, to a larger one, and even to still larger and larger domains; hence, rescaling the system. The reason behind this scalability is the necessary requirement for transforming equivocal meanings into evident ones. This is because all meanings in Qur’an must necessarily become evident sooner or later, as confirmed by Qur’an itself in the verse “it is for Us (God) to explain it (Qur’an)(in due course)”(75:19).

The system to be rescaled is the prospective database of Qur’anic meanings delivered within its verses, with no man-made preset confinement whatsoever. We are well aware not to add meanings erratically. So, what we will do is simply to mimic the method of Fiqh (Islamic jurisprudence), namely “Qiyās” (deductive analogy) in which scaling the field of its applicability through common cause(s), known as ‘illah’ (cause) between an older scale and a new larger one. Hence, we apply the ‘hukum’(dictum) – ‘illah’(Cause) rule on new states that have never been met before. That rule is to link every Hukum to its ‘illah(s). Wherever the ‘illah is fully satisfied, the Hukum is (should be) applicable. In a similar fashion to this foundational and well established rule of Fiqh, we do the same thing except that we apply it to the Qur’anic language, in which we need a new object recognition (Hukum) depending on its explicit attribute(s) (=! ‘illah(s)) mentioned in Qur’anic verses, in the hope of finding more appropriate intended (evident) meanings than the traditional equivocal ones. Hence the interest is in interpretability not applicability as it is in Fiqh. It may be better to name our objective ‘evident-ability’ than ‘interpret-ability’, but we assume that the proper interpretation has to be singled out as the evident one. After establishing the clear link for a proposed (Object-Attribute(s)) = (Hukum– ‘illah(s)) in the real world, we extract available explicit attribute(s) in the Qur’anic phrase that is (are) equivalent to the natural one(s). Once we confirm equivalence between the two sets, we recognize the object intended by the Qur’anic word/phrase delivering its attribute(s) as the natural object that is linked to its natural attributes.

This method is expected to confront many long standing obstacles in the orthodox Islamic exegesis. The convincing power of the method is so promising that it will help overcoming not only these obstacles, but also a series of challenges that the orthodox methodology itself could not succeed to overcome in its long struggle to do so. We enumerate the challenges in some detail to have some measure of the prospective resolution, and how urgent it is. Then we apply the new method to chapter (Sura) ‘Al-Ādiyāt’ by taking it as a prototype. Upon doing that, an object is well recognized out of the natural world. That object meets most of the explicit attributes in verses (100:1-5). Moreover, we will find that most of the aforementioned challenges can easily be resolved, and furthermore, the front and rear verses of Sura Al-Ādiyāt become causally tied together. The last outcome of this method is to have some predictions that can be

justified in the natural world. The whole process treats natural Qur'anic verses on an equal footing as natural phenomena, namely, in their need of being seamlessly interpreted. In so doing, we would have two sincere and authentic sources of information, namely 'Qur'an' and Nature, talking about same natural phenomena, hence a better understanding of which is anticipated. If challenges persist, or paradoxes evolve, authenticity of the sources or the methodology would be at stake.

A. Reasons That Hinder Islamic Civilization Revival

Current Islamic thought is confronted with two types of challenges; inherited and modern. Inherited ones are the historical theological conflicts between Islamic schools/scholars. Modern ones are the civilization and scientific challenges that are indicated by the almost null contribution of recognizable Islamic thought to modern civilization. Even though the distinction between the two types may seem sharp enough, they are actually inseparable on the level of foundational considerations; i.e. being stemming from an extended Islamic background. This inseparability was most probably the reason upon which some thinkers and critics refer to when they analyze the causes that impedes revival of Islamic civilization, or at least to have any perceptible contribution to the contemporary modern one, without losing its identity.

The problem with the analysis of those critics is that they refer to the word 'Islamic' as being synonymous to 'Qur'anic', where there is a difference that should not have been ignored. If that ignored difference is taken into account, the proper analysis should differentiate between 'Islam' as meaning 'Islamic revelation', which is actually equivalent to 'Qur'anic Islam', and 'Islamic inheritance' which is the multitude of distorted projections of 'Qur'anic revelation' on - as many as - what later came to be - Muslim cultures. The oversight of this distinction undermines any pretended critical analysis, as well as misguides any Islamic reformation or revival that may be built upon. This result – by itself – exposes this oversight and the analysis in which it is hidden, as an added challenge, as we will see, instead of its claim to resolve what has been accumulated of challenges; a blatant paradox.

This study uncovers the cultural fingerprints that dissolved into Islamic inheritance, and remained as impurities mixed within the Qur'anic exegesis, hence distorted the originally crystal-clear 'Qur'anic Islam', and paved the way for most of the challenges that Muslims are facing today. Praise be to Allah for preserving his own pure words by his Supreme Self, otherwise it would have been distorted alike by human interventions if it had been entrusted to them, much as previous heavenly revelations.

It is to be evoked what this true cause of Qur'anic meanings' partial distortions - carried over through obsolete world-views - may result in. It is not only a block to Muslims comprehension of the proper natural meanings, which is a Qur'anic mundane objective for a better grasp of this world reins, but it is even a block against some supreme goals for which Qur'an was revealed to human kind confirming its authenticity. A disastrous crisis should be added here, that is the permanent distortion of Qur'anic words through keeping circumstantial fingerprints of past Muslim cultures as an integrated part of God's Word, in a time that they are not necessarily certified as exact by many scholars in the least considerations! The result is that Muslims have inherited partially distorted Qur'anic semantics that stuck to the pure body of the Book through

official commentaries and translations. The preservation and dissemination of such dear wholesale heritage is equivalent to propagating a partially distorted reflection of ‘pristine Islam’; i.e. ‘Qur’anic Islam’.

B. Challenges to Restore “Qur’anic Islam”:

After an extended survey and contemplation on real challenges have accumulated along centuries and impeded Islam/Muslim revival, we collected the following challenges.

- 1- The aforementioned distortions were the outcomes of man-made dogmas that are still taken for granted up to this very day. One such dogma is that no more discoveries of meanings could ever be found in Qur’an! Why? – The dogma propagators say: if there have been any, the Prophet (PBUH) companions and followers would have known and disseminated! So, if there is any such a discovery, it is either a preserved one, hence it is not a discovery, or a false discovery, if it is not already known and preserved!
- 2- A second dogma proclaims that: All of Qur’anic verses, words, and phrases have been properly interpreted, especially among the first three generations in Islamic history; otherwise there would be some verses that will never be interpretable. And since there would be no more new interpretations afterwards (according to (1)), there would be a conflict with the wisdom of revelation of plain Qur’an to humanity as given in verse(36:69).

We reply to this dogma by saying that this is not necessarily true, unless we are on the last day of human existence on earth. But we are not. So there is still room of time for Qur’an to answer forthcoming generations of humanity; hence undiscovered answers in Qur’an are waiting for unuttered questions. That dogma of full established Qur’anic interpretations as perceived by first Arab encounters has penetrated Islamic orthodoxy and spread even to translations of the meaning of Qur’an. We read in the translation of Abdullah Yusuf Ali (verse 3:7 describing Qur’an)^[1]: “In it are verses basic or fundamental (of established meaning); they are the foundation of the Book: others are *allegorical*”.

We state that this translation is unacceptable for a number of reasons. We put here a proper one as: “In it (i.e. Qur’an) are evident verses; they are the foundation of the Book: others are *equivocal*” (3:7). We note that in this dogma proponent’s philosophy, the Arabic word “Mutashābihāt” which we translated as *equivocal* have been assigned the word *allegorical* as is shown above. It is incorrect because allegorical meanings will always be allegorical; this translation simply complies with the running dogma of closure of Qur’anic meanings. But, according to our vision presented in this work, these ‘equivocal’ verses are not yet interpreted as alleged by the proponents of inherited commentaries. Such type of verses in Qur’an represents our domain of work, in which to search for attributes (clues) plainly mentioned within the verses and whose objects can be naturally or factually recognized. We assume that this process of discovering meanings in Qur’an will

¹ <http://www.islam101.com/quran/yusufAli/QURAN/3.htm> (12/10/2018)

continue asymptotically with time for as long as there are future generations. Otherwise, there would be permanent ambiguities, which goes against the wisdom of the Scripture.

- 3- In the sense of dogma in (1), preserved commentaries are set equivalent to Qur'an. What modern Muslim has to do, is to revisit them, but not to exceed all of them, otherwise it would be deemed heresy. According to this mindset, no 'new' commentary would ever be part of Islam, however proper it may claim, and whatever evidence it may bring forth. All inherited commentaries, especially the first three generations, are collectively considered as part of Islam, however partially erroneous they are! This represents no problem for the dogma holders! The truth must be somewhere among the recorded voices. The only allowed task is to pick one up, not to add an extra pretended one. Any added meaning must be eccentric or heretical, unless it is a rephrase of a certified inherited one; case closed according to them.
- 4- Another dogma, that is no less extravagant, is the complete indifference to new scientific discoveries. Islam is self-sufficient according to this dogma holders. Understanding any verse in Qur'an must not depend on any non-'7th - 9th century' Arabic culture, implied in the Arabic linguistic interpretation. Since the best who can understand Qur'an are the first Muslim Arabs, Islam must comply with first Muslims world-view imbedded in their language. What makes things worse is that new scientific discoveries in modern times always come from non-Muslims. So, how come the understanding of Islam – according to these dogma proponents - depends on non-Muslim contributions?! In other words: Exegesis of Qur'anic verses was mainly based on a presumed static world-view; belonging to first few centuries after revelation, with a full silent exclusion of any possible update of which. But the acquisition of more knowledge on natural existence, which was developed specifically through the last few centuries, is continually pushing to revisit all related commentaries, and make necessary updates. This is fiercely objected by most orthodox Islamic academia inherited and still preached as it was 10 centuries ago without any update.
- 5- Another dogma is to restrict Qur'anic words such as 'Deed of Righteousness' and 'actions ordained by Allah on Muslims' as directed specifically to 'worshipping deeds and actions (rituals)'. No inclination comes in most commentaries to those deeds as to discover the creation of Allah, collect information, or manufacture better means for relieving hardness of life, in the sake of Allah. If such actions were rare in the past, giving an excuse for past Muslims to attain what good deeds relevant to their communities and humanity, there is no such excuse any more. The specific old meaning of deeds of worship alone stuck, and we find no regular academic Islamic education, let alone national strategies that include in its curriculum that good deeds include discovering the world, building modern industry and relieving harshness of life. If someone discusses such issues with dogma holders, they accuse him of mixing religious with secular issues! and that the verses "Behold! in the creation of the heavens and the earth, ..." (2:164), or

(3:190), or (10:101) should not be taken seriously as an imperative ordained by God on Muslims. They classify Qur'anic Ordains according to their dogmas, not correct their dogmas according to Qur'an.

- 6- Theological historical Islamic books are loaded with weak and disputed commentaries on the subject of creation and embedded causalities in natural processes, let alone unacceptable or extravagant ones. These commentaries were written down by commentators of Qur'an through the ages, where natural knowledge were severely limited. These books are still collectively certified by Islamic Academia as proper and valid for study and graduation degrees without any scientific demarcation. The reason behind its collective content validity is respect for esteemed commentators and fear of shaking dear heritage achievements and credibility, as well as any anticipated intricacies that may arise from any purification process that may be tried, especially in the absence of trusted and supported projects in this direction.
- 7- Translations of the meanings of Qur'an are presumed to be succinct and compact literal phraseology of Qur'anic verses. Unfortunately, in most of the time translators import meanings from commentaries according to past cultural understandings and include them – explicitly or implicitly - within the translated verses. These imported commentary additions are very dangerous. Simply they are erroneous in many cases. We always come across such errors. The reader will notice a few of them along these pages and how to replaced them with more proper and justifiable translations.
- 8- Most of conflicting Islamic Exegesis and Fiqh Schools were built upon different opinions of the founding scholars. But modern knowledge-based analysis can resolve many of these old conflicting opinions on a scientific basis. The dogmatic beliefs of these schools' followers prevent any possible prospective movements in this direction.
- 9- Confrontation between Qur'an and modern science ; being the legal representative of certified knowledge - is unavoidable, whether by anticipated serious Muslim scholars, or by Non-Muslims who are challenging Qur'anic credibility. On the one hand, educated Muslims adopting western scientific methodology can never think of any Qur'anic intervention in their celebrated education, let alone any update on their scientific beliefs through certifying an old or new Qur'anic interpretation. On the other hand, they may accept possible intervention of modern science in updating their inherited Qur'anic understanding, if they have any! The result would be a biased attitude and unfair confrontation that pushes again and again to equate science with 'The Philosophy of Living' and equate all religions – including 'Qur'anic Islam' - with 'The Philosophy of Dying'.
- 10- Western science's empirical foundations are partial in its informative power, and will never be definitive; hence numerous puzzles will always pop up from time to time, here and there. No rescue is expected because of the tradition of theoretical guessing used extensively in the current western methodology and escalated to the

level of scientific facts, as well as wishful thinking. By exposing many of the available information in Qur'an on relevant scientific subjects' and coupling it to empirical foundations, resolutions of many of these puzzles would be closer at hand. The stumbling block against that is the lack of academic support for individual efforts and collective work, as well as the absence of any educational strategies and future plans.

- 11- Miraculous claims in Qur'an (I'jaz) are often made by non-experts, leading to less cautious assessments. The majority of their claims are not definitive, not conclusive, and often blatantly false. To ensure the credibility of such claims, a respected authority should be established to review and evaluate them before any media publication. The process of extracting miraculous verses requires extensive scrutiny. Therefore, I'jaz should be the exclusive domain of qualified scholars specializing in both the Qur'an and relevant scientific fields. However, such experts seem to be scarce.
- 12- Continual updates are unavoidable on natural, cultural and social information. Therefore, adaptation of correlated Exegesis and Fatwas (religious rulings) is a must to be always in synch. They are man-made after all, even though they are based on 'Islamic Sacred Book'. The invariance of God's words is to be compared to the invariance of the laws of nature, not to a specific culture. What should be updated is human perception and reflections on both of these types of invariants. The majority of researchers on Islamic studies on relevant subjects of modern science miss this fact until now, and stuck to static views. Hence, they are resilient to adapt with this fast-changing world comprehension, with the consequence of lagging behind the evolution of science and data acquisition, and inadvertently hindering Islam's ability to meet contemporary challenges. The reaction of non-Muslims to that attitude is the view of Islam as a historical religion – like any other cultural religion - that has been vastly surpassed by science.
- 13- Numerous Islamic disputes are still open after centuries and sometimes a millennium of its original inception. Many of which can be resolved by modern scientific – and only scientific - inspection. Holders of these disputes do not believe in any 'scientific attitude'. The result is a dilemma. The patient does not believe in the treatment. So, he will never recover.
- 14- There are widespread attacks ^[2] on Qur'anic credibility based on presumed unfinished, disputed, or erroneous scientific claims, together with inherited historical commentaries cherished by attackers on the relevancy of Qur'anic verses to this modern time. All of these push on establishing a Scientific Qur'anic Academy to take real responsibility.
- 15- Failure of numerous Islamic revival projects shed light on a missing factor. If we combine the experiences gained out of such projects' failures, and our analysis of the reasons listed in the diagnosis developed here, and the new methodology we

² <http://wikiislam.net/> (12/10/2018)

propose, we think that a promising and successful revival project can be developed and avoid such failures.

These are the true reasons and challenges that impede people from knowing true Islam today. It is not part of ‘pristine Qur’anic Islam’, but seeded deliberately - may be inadvertently - in the body of religious edifice. As regarding the aforementioned challenges, mainstream authorities may be unaware of, or unqualified to respond to. These two attitudes gave rise to stigmatizing the originally pure ‘Qur’anic Islam’. Actually, these men committed a triple sin; the first: against Islam, the second: against Muslims, the third: against non-Muslims; by shielding them from ‘Qur’anic Islam’. Allah SWT ordered us to avoid such a pitfall when he taught us to say: “Our Lord! Make us not (bad representatives of your religion) for the Unbelievers (not to drift away)” (60-5).

C. The Aftermath of Islamic Revival Failures:

The negative outcomes of previous challenges, when left unsolved, produce mental frustration resulting from reasoning Schizophrenia, and resides in the Muslim thinkers’ collective mind. The severity of this frustration is most pronounced in those with a Western education, and it is directly proportional to their level of education ^[3]. This is true only for those who care about their Islamic heritage. We pose a relevant name for that mental frustration sickness as: ‘Heritage-Modernity Syndrome’.

Victims of this sickness come in 4 categories, depending on their type and level of education, and hence their own treatments to their symptoms:

1. Western-oriented Muslim Elites: They rush to get rid of realistic meanings of Qur’anic verses as understood by historical commentaries, and consequently abandon any literal real meanings, and find resort only in allegorical annotations. They are actually replicating similar behavior of western elites toward the Bible.
2. Heritage-oriented Sharia Scholars: They dismiss Western worldview and consider its achievements as mere technological advancements enclosed in flawed philosophies. Hence, they degrade western science as mere conjectures not to be taken seriously, whereas Qur’anic meanings – as received from older generations – is the full truth. In this way, they deny any confrontation, and negate the necessity of any resolution.
3. Half-Educated Muslims: they hang in-between Western and Islamic cultural heritage: Most of them seek refuge in a shortcut connecting two facets of reality; Qur’an and western science. The name of that shortcut is: I’jaz (miraculous verses).
4. Islamization Theoreticians: They emphasis values in the usage of science, and rephrase western science in a teleological context.

All of these categories miss the real causes of the sickness symptoms. Hence, their treatments are not expected to be of any profitable success to overcome their endurance, especially the first two categories. The third category has very little success since it hasn’t any project except for

³ ‘Schizophrenic’ as described by Nidhal Guessoum.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MmM1KEZervA&t=59s> (12/10/2018)

public media propaganda directed primarily to low to medium-level science education audience, even though its proponents may sometimes have real and true scientific verses to embrace, but they address them in an extremely superficial manner to such a degree that they can neither prove nor defend their thesis. The serious problem with their work is the great number of scientific blunders they commit. Thus the I'jazic tradition results in low level credibility in general, even when some of the subjects they address are scientifically valuable. That value may vanish through their false adjustments of Qur'anic meanings to meet incorrect scientific theories. The forth category^[4] is relatively closer to success, with a lot of good theoretical dialectics, except that it is heavily theoretical than practical. The only exception is 'Islamic Economy', which is a well-respected successful Islamic applied science in its own right.

D. Our New Methodology; 'Qur'anic Object Recognition:

Attaining a unified resolution to the above challenges is the biggest challenge in its own. We propose here a procedure that can be named: "Recognition Methodology"; that aims at 'recognizing the intended meanings of the words of God about his creation' by direct confrontation with actual realities through a real scientific investigation. The successful application will settle disputes – we suppose – on all of the above challenges.

The proposed methodology is based on full Integration of primary authoritative resources, which we restrict to two and only two: Qur'an and Nature (actual realities). Proper Prophet Hadeeth authority (PBUH) is included as a secondary resource to Qur'an as it is explicitly ordained within.

Credibility of Nature can be argued to branch also from Qur'an through frequent Qur'anic approvals of its credibility, same as Hadeeth, which is true. But, since it is not taken into account as Hadeeth by 'Islamic Magisterium', it has to be emphasized to be an independent authoritative resource since it is the creation of God in Islam as Qur'an is the word of God. A second reason for keeping it as a resource separate from Qur'an, is its precedence to Qur'an in the sequence of human perceptions; since humans receive natural sensual messages before any other type of message. A third reason is that it is not a linguistic one, as Qur'an and Hadeeth are. The forth reason is that the majority of subjects to be dealt with, by our new methodology, will be mainly natural phenomena (or actual realities in general) that should be independent of psychological affections. Unfortunately it is argued to the contrary by some scholars that nature is not an authoritative resource due to their conceptual view of a resource to be only a literally linguistic one. This attitude in itself is a technical challenge to be refuted and added to the list of challenges we enumerated above. This is not true, since meaning can always be extracted from natural phenomena, which is what physical theories actually are, and hence satisfy our demand for the definition of a credible informative independent resource.

By 'Nature' or 'Actual Realities' we mean: what is actually there, independently of human intervention of understanding by any means; linguistic, mathematical, numeric simulation or whatever. This resource may be comparable to 'Empirical Facts' in western science. But it is better to keep it distinct in its own, to avoid any alleged philosophy, or any loaded connotations of the western 'Empiricism' concept.

⁴ www.iiit.org (12/10/2018)

The proposed word: ‘Recognition’ in the title: “Object Recognition” is the literal meaning of the Arabic verb ‘ya[◌]ref’ which is very close to the English verbs: ‘identify’ and ‘recognize’. It is what to expect from the integration of the two extensive rich resources of information, Nature; the work of God, and Qur’an; the word of God, in a complementary fashion. One bit of information is given by one of the two resources and is then *identified* or be *recognized* by the other. The coupling of Nature with Qur’an as two complementary counterparts of information resources is expected to proliferate much more than to consider only one of them, especially when we find in Qur’an a host of explicit indicators to natural phenomena that demand close acquaintance with, to unlock ambiguous meanings in equivocal verses. That ambiguity is plainly expected in Qur’an, because of expressing yet-to-come information, transiting multiple generations, in well-known old Arabic words. A process that cannot be found in other than an authentic revelation from God.

E. ‘Recognition Methodology’ Strategy:

First of all, the verb ‘recognize’ together with the process of recognition is centralized in a number of Qur’anic verses, except that it has been overlooked because of a subtle difference with the verb ‘know’. The verb ‘ya[◌]ref,’ meaning ‘recognize,’ is often confused with the verb ‘ya[◌]lam,’ meaning ‘know.’. This confusion pushed commentators to make them interchangeable in many verses, where they are quite distinct.

The real meanings of the two words are as follows:

Know	=	Subject X has a set (s) of attributes Bs (X)
Recognize (identify)	=	Subject Y has the exact same set of attributes Bs(Y) as subject X,
That is, if	Bs (X) =	Bs (Y)
Then:	subject Y =	Subject X.

In other words, to recognize something is to correlate it with a previously known thing. When the two are compared through all their attributes, they turn out to be the same thing.

The problem of commentators on mingling ‘to know’ with ‘to recognize’ is transferred to translators. For example, In the translation of the meanings of Qur’an by (Abulla Yusuf Ali) we found Instances of “Ya[◌]ref” = ‘recognize’ that were improperly translated:

	Verse #	Qur’an	Translation (Abdullah Yusuf Ali)
1	12:58	فَدَخَلُوا عَلَيْهِ فَعَرَفَهُمْ وَهُمْ لَهُ مُنْكَرُونَ	they entered his presence, and he knew them, but they knew him not .
2	22:72	وَإِذَا تَنَلَّيْتُمْ أَيْتَانَا بَيِّنَاتٍ تَعْرِفُ فِي وُجُوهِ الَّذِينَ كَفَرُوا الْمُنْكَرَ	When Our Clear Signs are rehearsed to them, thou wilt notice a denial on the faces of the Unbelievers!
3	47:30	وَلَوْ نَشَاءُ لَأَرَيْنَاكُمْ فَلَعَرَفْتَهُمْ بِسِيمَاهُمْ وَلَتَعْرِفَنَّهُمْ فِي لَحْنِ الْقَوْلِ	We could have shown them up to thee, and thou shouldst have known them by their marks, but surely thou wilt know them by the tone of their speech!

4	2:273	يَحْسِبُهُمُ الْجَاهِلُ أَغْنِيَاءَ مِنَ التَّعَفُّفِ تَعْرِفُهُمْ بِسِيمَاهُمْ	the ignorant man thinks, because of their modesty, that they are free from want. Thou shalt know them by their (Unfailing) mark
5	27:93	وَقُلِ الْحَمْدُ لِلَّهِ سَيُرِيكُمْ آيَاتِهِ فَتَعْرِفُونَهَا وَمَا رَبُّكَ بِغَافِلٍ عَمَّا تَعْمَلُونَ	And say: "Praise be to Allah, Who will soon show you His Signs, so that ye shall know them"
6	2:146, 6:20	الَّذِينَ آتَيْنَاهُمُ الْكِتَابَ يَعْرِفُونَهُ كَمَا يَعْرِفُونَ أَبْنَاءَهُمْ	The people of the Book know this as they know their own sons
7	7:46	وَعَلَى الْأَعْرَافِ رِجَالٌ يَعْرِفُونَ كُلًّا بِسِيمَاهُمْ	and on the heights will be men who would know every one by his marks
8	12:62	اجْعَلُوا بِضَاعَتَهُمْ فِي رِحَالِهِمْ لَعَلَّهُمْ يَعْرِفُونَهَا إِذَا انْقَلَبُوا إِلَى أَهْلِهِمْ	put their stock-in-trade into their saddle-bags, so they should know it only when they returned to their people
9	7:48	وَنَادَى أَصْحَابُ الْأَعْرَافِ رِجَالًا يَعْرِفُونَهُمْ بِسِيمَاهُمْ	The men on the heights will call to certain men whom they will know from their marks
10	55:41	يُعْرِفُ الْمُجْرِمُونَ بِسِيمَاهُمْ	the sinners will be known by their marks
11	33:59	ذَلِكَ أَدْنَىٰ أَنْ يُعْرِفَنَ فَلَا يُؤْذِنَنَّ	that they should be known (as such) and not molested

Table (1): Instances of confusing the verb: “know” with “recognize” in translating the verb “Ya^{ar}ef” by “Abdullah Yusuf Ali” in some Qur’anic verses.

In all these instances, the words; ‘Know’, ‘notice’ should be replaced with ‘recognize’. The translator has done it correctly in other instances, {(2:89), (5:83), (83:24), (23:69), (16:83)}

Our strategy is simply an extension of this traditional human cognitive instinct of recognizing meanings through identification of addressed objects. Actually it is the primary natural way of grasping intended meaning of any speech, i.e. when one is addressing some anonymous object and whoever is listening to him. The listener will try to recognize (=identify) what the speaker is talking about through its collective attributes. It was even used by commentators and the prophet’s companions (PBUH). The traditional meaning of the word ‘Al-^{ar}diyāt’ in Sura Al-^{ar}diyāt as ‘Horses’ or ‘Camels’ – as given in old commentaries - was based on the same cognitive process of object recognition (within the world-view of the commentator). So, we are not inventing an eccentric methodology, it is only the world-view has been extended and is still extending with more knowledge gained. It is simply an exposition of two informative statements. These two statements must come separately, either from a given source at two different times, or from two different sources. Since Qur’an has already been revealed with no more additions (other than prophet’s Hadeeth), then any equivocal word or phrase in Qur’an can only be recognized using a source of information different from direct revelation. This source is what we identified as ‘bare Nature’. This is because ‘bare Nature’ is the work of God with no involvement of whoever may proclaim. Theories about Nature are not the same as bare Nature, and therefore cannot be considered reliable sources of information. Therefore, a process of distillation of bare Natural information must be done in a similar fashion as the process of distillation of bare Qur’anic meanings out of inherited Muslim heritage, which can then be identified as Theories of Qur’anic Interpretations.

So, what we are actually adding here is a more elaborate use of this method of meaning clarification through Nature as a new source of information besides Qur'an. By elaboration, we mean that we extend the database of 'Objects' Attributes' that should be available to dig into, in the process of recognizing what Qur'anic verses are talking about. The resource of objects' database extension is modern scientific 'Bare Discoveries'. So, we call for an open categorical database, with no restriction in space or time. And here comes what we call 'Scalability of Qur'anic Validity and Applicability' as a process that takes place on the new territories discovered and expanded by this database. This process of database extension is actually to comply with what Allah is saying in Qur'an: 'Say: "Behold all that is in the heavens and on earth"'(10-101).

We have to note here that the process of object recognition is explicitly mentioned in Qur'an, but has often been overlooked. The reader can find it in the verse: 'And say: "Praise be to Allah, Who will show you His Signs, so that ye shall *recognize* them"' (27:93). Unfortunately, this verse was not properly translated as we noted above in (table.1), where the Arabic word "Fata^rrefūnahā" was translated to 'ye shall know them' whereas the proper translation should be: 'ye shall *recognize* them'. The key point of this paper is that verse (27:93) is pivotal. The road that we bring forth here is the technical "Object-Recognition" road, which insistently demands a new source of information, in order for the process of recognition to be functional. That second source of information we identify as 'Nature', which should not to be confused with 'Modern Science' however entangled they are. Whoever denies that road must come with a different trusted source, if he can find any! Otherwise, equivocal verses will remain equivocal forever! or be burdened with distracted meanings that have been passed down through the ages, based solely on the linguistic preferences or non-technical⁵ recognition of objects - close at hand - by commentators.

F. 'Recognition Methodology' Procedure:

The available bare information of the Qur'anic Subject that is under investigation is collected from the two independent resources: Qur'an & 'A Proposed Natural Phenomenon'. The information from each resource is presumed to be partially ambiguous and insufficient 'as a full-fledged visual representation of the phenomenon' if taken separately. When information is confronted from the two resources together, and the natural phenomenon happens to be the true target phenomenon of Qur'anic verses, a state of complementarity is reached, and an identifiable and more focused objective is manifested.

Next comes our exposition for what that integration may look like.

G. 'Integration-Algorithm' Method:

In this method we seek to integrate available information from Qur'an and Nature in a process similar to that of solving two algebraic equations. In each equation we have a combination of terms; partially unknown. Similarly, in an extracted phrase from Qur'an, whether it comes out as part of one verse or as a number of verses, contiguous or distributed in different chapters (Suras). We visualize the object of the phrase(s) as the equation head on the left side, representing the name of the object of interest, and a number of attributes describing that object

⁵ (= primitive and superficial)

in the phrase as the algebraic terms on the right side of the equation. Then we confront this set of attributes of the Qur’anic phrase with parallel attributes from the given proposed natural phenomenon; one by one attribute. This proposed phenomenon and its attributes represent the second algebraic equation. The general case is that we will look for the phenomenon – among many tentative phenomena - whose attributes goes along the best with those of the Qur’anic phrase attributes. That best phenomenon is to be pushed forward as a candidate explanation for the designated object in the Qur’anic phrase, and hence, it is what to be recognized as the target of the Qur’anic verses by the ‘Recognition Methodology’. That phenomenon may be certain – if substantiated enough – or just be the best explanation available, until it is pushed aside later by some other phenomenon that is even more fitting.

The ‘Recognition Process’ considered here – which we present as our methodology for Qur’anic discoveries - takes us from explicit given attributes to phenomenal recognition. It is the reverse process to the process of discovery in exact sciences, where we observe a given named phenomenon in Nature, followed by extracting whatever attributes it may has.

H. Application of ‘Recognition Methodology’ to Sura Al-^cĀdiyāt, verses (1-5):

The phenomenon we present now to exemplify this methodology is ‘Northern Lights’ or ‘Aurora borealis’, ‘Aurora australis’; or simply: ‘Aurora’^[6] (see Box: 1) in which we confront its designated attributes with corresponding explicit attributes of Sura Al-^cĀdiyāt, verses(1-5) (see Table 2, and Figure 2).

The two sets of attributes on the two sides are assumed to be semantically parallel; one to the other, where known common attributes represent the facets of connections, or links. Unknown attributes on one side are linked to its known counterparts on the other side, allowing for the discovery of their meaning when equality is confirmed. In this way, more knowledge is gained on the phenomenon, gaps in understanding are filled, and more confidence is gained in the correlation of the two resources regarding the common phenomenon, and how far the unitary concept behind the procedure is manifested?!

Sura Al-^cĀdiyāt, verses(1-5):

	Verse #	Qur’an: Sura Al- ^c Ādiyāt (100)	Translation (the Author Translation)
1	100:1	وَالْعَادِيَاتِ ضَبْحًا	By the runners, panting.
2	100:2	فَالْمُورِيَاتِ قَدْحًا	Glowing moiré, of ignition.
3	100:3	فَالْمُغِيرَاتِ صُبْحًا	Onrushing at dawn.
4	100:4	فَأَنْزَلْنَ بِهِ نَقْعًا	Thereby We stir hazy dust.
5	100:5	فَوَسَطْنَ بِهِ جَمْعًا	And therein We centralize a host.

⁶ <http://www.informationin.com/2013/06/how-auroras-work.html> (12/10/2018)
<http://www.aurora-service.eu/aurora-school/aurora-borealis/> (12/10/2018)
<http://www.skyandtelescope.com/observing/keep-track-of-the-aurora/> (12/10/2018)
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aurora> (12/10/2018)

Table 2: This is the author's translation⁷. The author adhered to the literal wording in Arabic as closely as possible, which he termed 'bare information.' The majority of other translations of Qur'anic meanings (more than 60 of them) carry interpretations that are not explicitly stated in the original Qur'anic verses, potentially leading to a loss of the intended meaning.

Box 1: Aurora: (Etymology: from the Latin word for "dawn, morning light")

A stream of charged particles is continually released from the upper atmosphere of the Sun in the form of outgoing wind, known as: ‘Solar Wind’. It consists of mostly electrons, protons and alpha particles. When these charged particles strike the upper Earth's atmosphere, they disturb its magnetosphere, resulting in ionization and excitation of atmospheric constituents, thus emitting lights of varying color and complexity. When it reaches lower atmosphere, sounds – much like animal sounds – are born.

The paths of incident charged particles are not random, but directed by the earth’s magnetic field lines and drift along them with a spiral action and fall down toward the magnetic poles on earth as near as their paths allow. So its downfall is not a smooth one, but spiraling in pitches, much like steps. Hence it is running down.

Since the magnetic field lines are not focused in a central spot on its magnetic pole, the domain of fall down, as indicated by emerging colored lights, is a circle around each of the magnetic poles. The aggregation of these downfall of particles forms a circle around the magnetic pole. Within that circle converge most of earth’s magnetic field lines.

We take note here of a set of attributes of this phenomenon: Solar charged particles (*running*, producing *animal-like sounds*, *emitting glowing lights*, *occurring at dawn*, disturbing air constituents (unknown to the author before investigating the natural phenomenon), and *grouping in a circle enclosing converging* magnetic field lines)

Figure (1): Pictorial representation of the mechanism behind the phenomenon of Aurora^[8]

⁷ <https://kazaaber.blogspot.com/2023/07/blog-post.html> (Al-Otrojja Translation of the literal wording of Qur'an)

⁸ <https://modernsurvivalblog.com/space/aurora-the-bright-side-of-solar-doom-and-gloom/> (12/10/2018)
<https://antarcticarctic.wordpress.com/2013/07/04/aurora-australis/> (12/10/2018)

Figure (2): Confronting Attributes of Sura 'Al-Ādiyāt (1-5) (right) with the set of attributes of the Aurora phenomenon (Left).

I. Mathematical Procedure:

Let $Q(s)$ be the Qur'anic statement on subject (s). In general it has components $q1(s), q2(s), \dots, qi(s)$, hence:

$$(1) \quad Q(S) = \{q1(s) + q2(s) + \dots + qi(s)\}$$

Likewise, let $N(t)$ be the Natural statement on the subject (t). By a similar token, we get:

$$(2) \quad N(T) = \{n1(t) + n2(t) + \dots + nj(t)\}$$

Now, we confront the two sets of algebraic terms (attributes) in (1) and (2), one by one: (= ? Means: equality check)

$$q1(s) = ? n1(t), \quad q2(s) = ? n2(t), \quad q3(s) = ? n3(t), \dots$$

In the optimal case, of satisfying all terms (attributes) with equal sign, we should have:

$$Q(S) = N(T)$$

The conclusive result is:

$S = T$; meaning that Qur'anic statement (S) is **coincident** with the exact phenomenon (T).

If not all terms are satisfied with the equal sign, being not yet justifiable, for instance:

$$q6(s) = ? n6(t)$$

Then, the two equalities:

$$(3) \quad S = T \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad [q6(s) = n6(t)]$$

Must be satisfied together (supposing that $\{ni(t)\}$ is a closed set.

By applying the result in (3) to our case study of verses of Sura Al-^cĀdiyāt(1-5) (figure 2).

We get:

S= ‘Al-^cĀdiyāt’(1-5), T= ‘Radiation (Solar Wind) causing Aurora’

q6 (s) = ‘Hazing dust’, n6 (t) = ?

With all other terms satisfied as given in figure (2) above.

Thus,

If S = T, then n6 (t) = ‘Hazing dust’

Which means that:

if ‘Al-^cĀdiyāt’(1-5)) is the ‘Radiation causing Aurora’,

Then: ‘Radiation causing Aurora’ must be a source of hazy dust.

If this condition is fully justified, then we get an ‘Overarching Object Recognition’ Z(S), satisfying:

$$Z(S) = Q(S) + N(S)$$

Where Z(S) is the resulting collective statement about the subject, as given by God’s Work; Nature, and God’s Word; Qur’an. And it should be treated as ‘the Most Comprehensive Legitimate Interpretation’ (MCLI).

Prediction:

The result [$n_6(t) = \text{‘Hazing Dust’}$] is a prediction of our method. It means that within the Aurora phenomenon there is an agitation of dust that makes the sky hazy. The reason of which can be understood as that the tracks of radiation causing Aurora are the source of exciting Dust / Aerosol / Haze through a number of stimuli: Dynamo Effect^[9], heating effect^[10], and ionization

⁹ - Blanc, M., and A. Richmond (1980), The ionospheric disturbance dynamo, J. Geophys. Res., 85(A4), 1669–1686, doi:[10.1029/JA085iA04p01669](https://doi.org/10.1029/JA085iA04p01669) (12/10/2018)

- Xiong, C., H. Lüher, and B. G. Fejer (2015), Global features of the disturbance winds during storm time deduced from CHAMP observations. J. Geophys. Res. Space Physics, 120, 5137–5150. doi: [10.1002/2015JA021302](https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JA021302). (12/10/2018)

¹⁰ Kurihara, J., et al. (2009), Temperature enhancements and vertical winds in the lower thermosphere associated with auroral heating during the DELTA campaign, J. Geophys. Res., 114, A12306, doi:[10.1029/2009JA014392](https://doi.org/10.1029/2009JA014392). (12/10/2018)
<http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2009JGRA..11412306K> (12/10/2018)

effect^[11]. All of these effects stroke planetary atmospheres in general^[12] including our planet Earth. On Earth it represents a vast field of research^[13]. The evidences supporting Sun's radiation causing Aurora on earth's wind system, and the mysterious Arctic Haze^[14], are numerous, but only a serious research program can link this wide spectrum of Aurora effects on earth to the weather system can prove that.

J. Recognition of Verses:

The strategy just described is simply an extension of the traditional human habit of recognition, as we have said above. It is the identification of a thing or a person by previous encounters and known attributes. In the Arabic Language there are two verbs 'ya'lam يعلم' and 'ya'raf يعرف' that may be translated as 'to know' because of having the same core meaning. But, an elaborate translation takes care of the subtle nuance which identify 'ya'raf' with 'recognize'. In this sense, what we have done above is exactly the process described in the Qur'anic verse:

”وَقُلِ الْحَمْدُ لِلَّهِ سِيرِيكُمْ آيَاتِهِ فَتَعْرِفُونَهَا“ (Sura Al-Naml 27:93)

Which according to Abdullah Yusuf Ali, its translation is: 'And say: "**Praise be to Allah, Who will soon show you His Signs, so that ye shall *know* them**".

But, according to our analysis, this is not accepted. The proper translation should be: "**And say: 'Praise be to Allah, Who will show you His Signs, and ye will *recognize* them**".

The whole difference between these two translations and methodologies behind is to acknowledge beforehand whether the Qur'anic text is self-sufficient in closure of meaning of equivocal verses (inherited methodology) or not self-sufficient (our methodology). Our thesis

¹¹ - Hosokawa, K., and Y. Ogawa (2015), Ionospheric variation during pulsating aurora, J. Geophys. Res. Space Physics, 120, 5943–5957, doi:[10.1002/2015JA021401](https://doi.org/10.1002/2015JA021401). (12/10/2018)

<http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2015JGRA..120.5943H>. (12/10/2018)

- Sojka, J.J. Space Sci Rev (2017) 212: 1041. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-017-0379-z> (12/10/2018)

<http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2017SSRv..212.1041S>. (12/10/2018)

- Takahashi, T., et al. (2017), Depletion of mesospheric sodium during extended period of pulsating aurora, J. Geophys. Res. Space Physics, 122, 1212–1220, doi:[10.1002/2016JA023472](https://doi.org/10.1002/2016JA023472). (12/10/2018)

<http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2017JGRA..122.1212T>. (12/10/2018)

¹² - Gérard, J. C.; Dols, V.; Grodent, D.; Waite, J. H.; Gladstone, G. R.; Prangé, R. (1995), Simultaneous observations of the Saturnian aurora and polar haze with the HST/FOC. Geophysical Research Letters, Volume 22, Issue 20, p. 2685-2688.

<http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/1995GeoRL..22.2685G>. (12/10/2018).

- Bhardwaj, Anil; Gladstone, G. Randall, (2000), Auroras on Saturn, Uranus, and Neptune. Advances in Space Research, Volume 26, Issue 10, p. 1551-1558. [10.1016/S0273-1177\(00\)00096-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0273-1177(00)00096-X). (12/10/2018).

<http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2000AdSpR..26.1551B>. (12/10/2018).

¹³ See for instance: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/High_Frequency_Active_Auroral_Research_Program (12/10/2018).

¹⁴ - Glenn E. Shaw (1995), The Arctic Haze Phenomenon, Geophysical Institute, University of Alaska, Fairbanks, Alaska. [10.1175/1520-0477\(1995\)076<2403:TAHP>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477(1995)076<2403:TAHP>2.0.CO;2) (12/10/2018)

- Marvin S. Soroos, (010), The Odyssey of Arctic Haze toward a Global Atmospheric Regime. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00139157.1992.9930938> (12/10/2018).

here is that it is the set of [Qur'an + Nature] is the self-sufficient, but none of them is self-sufficient by its own (in the realm of Natural knowledge and similar proliferating knowledge). That is, unless we engage with Nature sensically, we will never know what Qur'an is talking about, as far as the equivocal verses are concerned. The lowest extreme of knowledge, for an observer, is to lose all his senses to this world. No doubt that Qur'an will then be of no use to him. For that extreme observer, Qur'anic description “*Deaf, dumb, and blind, who do not reason*” (8:22) will be fully satisfied. For the uppermost extreme observer, it is to know everything about the universe. Only then will Qur'an be fully understandable (evident). Partial sense perception and comprehension (incomprehension) of the world entails partial acquaintance (equivocation) of Qur'an. Hence, the more knowledge we gain about the universe (Nature), the more we understand the implied messages about God's creation delivered in Qur'an. That gain in 'evident natural knowledge' turns these Qur'anic implied equivocal messages into explicit ones.

So, understanding Qur'anic equivocal verses by humanity is a function of knowledge gain since Qur'an was revealed, which in turn is a function of time; i.e. humanity lifetime. And that is the meaning of the verse: “... هَلْ يَنْظُرُونَ إِلَّا تَأْوِيلَهُ يَوْمَ يَأْتِي تَأْوِيلَهُ يَقُولُ الَّذِينَ نَسُوهُ مِنْ قَبْلُ... ” (7:53) which I translate as: “**Do they just wait for its full interpretation? On the day on which its full interpretation comes (disclosed), those who disregarded it before will say ...**” which is translated differently by (Abdullah Yusuf Ali) according to the traditional view of a closed and static Qur'anic Meanings; as: “**Do they just wait for the final fulfillment of the event (Great Prophecy of Qur'an; the Day of Judgement)? On the day the event is finally fulfilled, those who disregarded it before will say ...**”. Actually, the full interpretation ‘*Ta’weel* تَأْوِيلٌ’ is to happen only when humanity gains almost all of the worldly knowledge that runs in consonance with Qur'an. And this happens only at the closing chapter of humanity's lifespan. So, the intended meaning of the word ‘*Ta’weel* تَأْوِيلٌ’ – which its core meaning is ‘**interpretation**’ - in this verse is ‘*the exposition of full true meanings of all its equivocal verses*’. It is not the physical fulfillment of the last events specifically as has traditionally been understood by scholars. The issue here is that full understanding of its remaining equivocal verses is concomitant with the last days of humanity; hence they are very close in time. This understanding can also be said on the verse about prophet Joseph, that was translated by (Abdullah Yusuf Ali) as: “**O my father! this is the fulfillment of my vision of old! Allah hath made it come true!**”(12:100); said Joseph; namely, its translation should be: “**O my father! this is the interpretation of my vision of old! Allah hath made it come true!**” because the meaning came along with the fulfillment itself. The moral of my argument here is that [‘*Ta’weel* تَأْوِيلٌ’ is a word of *cognition*, not a word of ‘Action’].

K. ‘Recognition’ As A Procedural Methodology to Achieve ‘Interpretation’:

In ‘Tafseer’ – of verses which are necessarily evident - the meaning is known to scholars, but in *Ta’weel* – of verses which are necessarily equivocal - the meaning is not known by any means, up to a time. This is because sufficient components of the meaning are satisfied in Tafseer, but not (yet) in *Ta’weel*. *Ta’weel* is possible only when meaning sufficiency is achieved. This happens only when the term of exposing its meaning is reached. By then it is just a potential Tafseer as any other older tafseer. That specified term is the time of

availability of information from outside the Qur’anic text, otherwise it would have been known by first Muslims. The means of disclosing hidden/implied meanings could only be done through Recognition’ of newly discovered phenomena/objects/events - relevant to the verses in question - that were previously unknown.

This analysis implies that there is no successful deductive linguistic ‘Ta’weel’, to say the truth. It is just a trial to achieve tafseer. If it is successful, it is tafseer and the verses are evident; otherwise it is just a failed trial, and more information is needed to the rescue. The decisive criteria for a verse/phrase/word to cross the gap from being equivocal to becoming evident is through overcoming deficiency of absolutely necessary information. The role of scholars is shuffling, disclosing, and refining meanings. The end of term for each equivocal verse to become evident is in the hands of whoever sent Qur’an; God. This is according to the verse: **“It is pending upon us the clarification thereof.”**(75:19). That is to disclose its evident meaning, so that it becomes tafseer(able), after it was before that ta’weel(able) only.

L. Discussion

Now, after succeeding in exposing/recognizing the proper meanings of Sura Al-Ādiyāt (100:1-5) , it is necessary to check our method of recognition, as applied in this task, to see how far it has achieved in overcoming the list of challenges we started with. We will list them again in the same sequence, and put a closing remark to each of them. (Note: We are referring only in all of the following remarks to equivocal verses in Qur’an – Which amounts to a few hundred verses - as exemplified by verses (100:1-5). So, evident verses are out of discussion, since they are evident, i.e. fully understood and interpreted by proper Commentaries):

- 1- The dogma of no more discoveries of meanings could ever be found in Qur’an– (Falsified).
- 2- The dogma that all of Qur’anic verses, words, and phrases have been properly interpreted– (Falsified).
- 3- The consideration that preserved commentaries are equivalent in meaning to Qur’an– (Falsified).
- 4- The custom of complete indifference to new scientific discoveries – (Falsified).
- 5- Sharp dichotomy of religious deeds as rituals only, from worldly deeds as non-religious– (Falsified).
- 6- Theological historical Islamic books being loaded with weak and disputed commentaries by current scientific standards, let alone unacceptable or extravagant ones – (Confirmed in the realm of natural phenomena).
- 7- Translations of the meanings of Qur’an through commentaries loaded with obsolete cultural understandings – (Confirmed).

In this context we propose a new translation of verses (100:1-5), and set it free from any implied cultural projection; the historical one, or the new one we are presenting here. To make the comparison explicit, we compare our proposed translation (Left) with (Abdullah Yusuf Ali) translation (right).

Proposed Translation	Abdullah Yusuf Ali Translation
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Al- ^ع Ādiyāt (The Runners) 1- By the runners, in panting. 2- Glowing moiré, of ignition. 3- Onrushing at dawn. 4- Thereby We stir hazy dust. ^[15] 5- And therein We centralize a host.	The <u>Courser*</u> , The <u>Chargers</u> 1. By the (<u>Steeds</u>) that run, with panting (<u>breath</u>), 2. And strike sparks of fire, 3. And <u>push home the charge</u> in the morning, 4. And raise the dust in <u>clouds</u> the while, 5. And <u>penetrate</u> forthwith into the midst (<u>of the foe</u>) en masse
*All underlined words are reflections of the cultural understanding projections on the process of translation. We propose to free Qur’anic translation from any such projection; old or new. Any equivocal word should be translated literally. Only through accompanying commentaries, meanings can be disclosed and justified, but left open for new updates of further justifications or refutations. It is simply a matter of scientific research on the meanings of God’s words as much as the scientific research on the meanings of God’s creation (Natural Phenomena).	

Table (2): A Proposed Translation Free from Cultural Influence

8- Modern knowledge-based analysis can resolve many of the old conflicting opinions - (Al-^عĀdiyāt was given two interpretations: Chargers (As given by Prophet Companion: Ebn Abbas), and Camels (As given by Prophet Companion: Ali Ben Abi-Talib)). Our analysis negates the two interpretations and proposes and justifies the phenomenon of ‘Aurora’ as extremely close to description of the verses, if not coincident with. Clearly it was completely unknown to the Arabs. What is even more intriguing is that its attributes were uncovered scientifically only recently to all of humanity).

9- Confrontation between Qur’an and modern science being unavoidable – (We confirmed that it is in favor of the credibility of Qur’an. This is against the wishes of some Non-Muslims and westerly educated Muslims who endeavor to prove the irrelevancy[16]).

10- Western science empirical foundations are partial in its informative power – (We found a number of sources that referred to the puzzle of Arctic Haze and the mechanism behind. This puzzle can presumably be resolved with the verse: “With which we stir hazing dust”(100-4)).

11- Miraculous claims in Qur’an (I’jaz) are practiced predominantly by non-expert Muslims- (We consider our analysis presented in this work to be a prototype for prospective I’jaz, not as a direct objective, but as a byproduct of serious scientific investigation).

12- Adaptation of Islamic Exegesis and Fatwas on newly discovered truths is a must – (Confirmed).

¹⁵ See for instance:

Science News Volume 187 issue 8 2015 [doi 10.1002/scin.2015.187008018] Crockett, Christopher -- [Atom & cosmos- Martian aurora, high-altitude dust surprise scientists.](http://www.arcticobservingsummit.org/sites/arcticobservingsummit.org/files/Bullard_AOS16_ShortStatement.pdf)
http://www.arcticobservingsummit.org/sites/arcticobservingsummit.org/files/Bullard_AOS16_ShortStatement.pdf (12/10/2018).
<http://www.hlccd.org/> (12/10/2018).
<https://americangeophysicalunion.tumblr.com/post/126422243548/hello-everyone-dust-storms-are-a-real-problem> (12/10/2018).

¹⁶ <http://kazaaber.blogspot.com/2014/12/2.html> (12/10/2018).

13- Numerous Islamic disputes are still open for investigation. Many of which can be resolved by modern scientific inspection. Holders of these disputes do not believe in any ‘scientific attitude’ – (Supported).

14- Sporadic attacks on Qur’anic Credibility, together with inherited historical commentaries cherished by attackers on the relevancy of Qur’anic verses to this modern time – (Refuted).

15- Failure of numerous Islamic revival projects shed light on a missing link – (We hope that this missing thing is the “Object Recognition” method which is close at hand as presented above).

M. An Off-Shoot Illumination of Our New Interpretation of Sura Al-^cĀdiyāt:

After establishing the interpretation of Al-^cĀdiyāt as the solar wind of charged particles incident on earth and directed by the earth’s magnetic field in the process, we noticed a prominent link between the call to witness of God to this magnificent phenomenon, and the ending verses of the Sura.

In tafseer and Arabic rhetoric, there is a rule that says: "Rear phrase should follows front one", meaning: ‘A full statement can be divided into front and rear phrases, then the rear phrase should be (causally linked to/directed by/reduced to) – the front phrase’. It simply means that the ending phrase in a statement should be a reflection or an illumination of/by the front phrase.

According to our Interpretation of the front phrase of Sura Al-^cĀdiyāt (the collection of verses (1-5) as describing ‘Aurora’), the rear collection of verses (100: 9, 10) describe two major events on resurrection; namely “when that which is in the graves is scattered out” (100:9), “And that which is in (human) hearts is collected”(100:10).

Now we can visualize what is happening on Aurora as a glamorous exposition on the face of scattered magnetic field out of one pole of earth (resembling scattering of resurrected people out of graves), and on the accumulating magnetic lines of force to the other pole (resembling collecting what is in the human hearts). The whole show of the day of resurrection is a reflection of these two events, as much as the aurora display is a reflection of emanation and recollection of magnetic field lines.

The ending verse says: “Their Lord had been well-acquainted with them that Day”. It reflects that God is acquainted with the resurrection day, as much as he manifested to you in the front verses what is happening on the resurrection of magnetic field lines out of earth and recollecting them according to his ‘Natural’ plan. On the verge of these two events on the day of resurrection there will be scenes not far from Aurora stupendous scenes. What a simile?! (figure 3)

Figure (3): Similes of Sura Al-Ādiyāt according to our Interpretation/Tafseer.
 Courtesy of Picture Source [17].

Conclusion

The methodology presented above can be considered, in a pictorial view, as a process that invests a dual resourceful ‘bank of information’: (Qur’an + Nature), upon which an integrated science can be built. In this view, Qur’an proves to be a ‘literal’ universe in its own right, with God’s words as its foundational constituents and laws; although finite in number, still infinite in instances of discoverable events that satisfy them. It is much like the natural universe, in which foundational constituents and laws are finite, though the proliferation of which are infinite.

We are calling for establishing a research program to scale up the applicability of Qur’anic verses of Sura Al-Ādiyāt into a scientific Qur’anic Research Program. It is only one example of what Qur’an keeps for generations to come, beyond which there are numerous examples to investigate and satiate our scientific appetite with the richness of ‘Qur’anic Islam’ together with virgin Nature.

¹⁷ <http://discovermagazine.com/2017/jul-aug/auroras> (12/10/2018).